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TALLHEDA

TRANSFORMING ACCESS TO EXCELLENCE WITH SUCCESSFUL ALLIANCES OF HIGHER
EDUCATION IN DIGITAL AGRICULTURE

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Other authors	Dimitrios Tsolis, Panagiotis Panopoulos, Eugenia Karamouzi		
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- The present document is of TALLHEDA project request on *Best Practices for gender Equality and Inclusive Education in widening HEIs*.
- The present document utilizes the terminology of European Commission Glossary¹

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¹ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary_en

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List of Abbreviations

DA: Digital Agriculture

HEI: Higher Education Institutes

GEP: Gender Equality Plan

EU: European Union

EIGE: European Institute for Gender Equality

p.p: percentage points

ICT: Information and Communication Technology

STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

GBV: Gender-Based Violence

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

EENEE: European Expert Network on Economics of Education

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

PISA: Programme for International Student Assessment

GEAR: Gender Equality in Academia and Research

Glossary

Sex: The biological characteristics of a person, predominantly female or male ²

Gender: The socially constructed attributes, roles, activities, responsibilities and needs predominantly connected to being male or female in given societies or communities at a given time³

Inclusive education: A European pillar of social rights where *“Everyone has the right to quality and inclusive education, training and life-long learning in order to maintain and acquire skills that enable them to participate fully in society and manage successfully transitions in the labour market”*⁴

Gender equality: Promoting equal economic independence for women and men, closing the gender pay gap, advancing gender balance in decision making, ending gender based violence and promoting gender equality beyond the EU⁵

Gender identity: Individuals’ internal, personal sense of their gender⁶

² https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/sex_en

³ [https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/gender_en#:~:text=Definition\(s\),communities%20at%20a%20given%20time](https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/gender_en#:~:text=Definition(s),communities%20at%20a%20given%20time)

⁴ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/focus-topics/improving-quality/inclusive-education>

⁵ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality_en#:~:text=Promoting%20equal%20economic%20independence%20for,gender%20equality%20beyond%20the%20EU

⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-09/legal_gender_recognition_in_the_eu_the_journeys_of_trans_people_towards_full_equality_sept_en.pdf

1. Objective

The present document is of TALLHEDA project's request on *Best Practices for gender Equality and Inclusive Education in widening HEIs* as part of the cross-fertilization activities of WP2 and particularly T2.4. TALLHEDA aims to accelerate research performance of the participating widening HEIs (AUA and UNSFA) via sharing standardized research protocols and best practices in Digital Agriculture (DA) in priority cross-cutting topics including Gender equality and inclusive education, among others.

The main objectives of the present document were **1)** to deliver a protocol for identifying and documenting Best Practices in mainstreaming gender equality and inclusive education in HEIs and, **2)** to provide representative documented examples of such Best Practices. Initially, the document presents an overview of the importance of gender equality and inclusiveness, focusing on strategies towards mainstreaming gender equality with emphasis on TALLHEDA widening countries. Subsequently, the benefits of gender equality and inclusive education in HEIs along with the relevance to the EU policy era are discussed to reveal current obstacles and proposed tackling solutions and strategies. Particular emphasis is given to the TALLHEDA widening HEIs current situation with respect to mainstreaming gender equality and inclusive education.

The European Commission utilizes Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) as the main policy instrument to promote institutional changes in tertiary educational organizations with respect to gender equality and inclusive education. However, it seems that, despite efforts and the fact that all European HEIs are obliged to have a GEP, gender inequalities persist in the European tertiary educational system including Research and Innovation, with a notable gap between the adoption of policies and strategies at EU and national level, and their implementation at the institutional level. In this context, applied strategies aiming at making a shift towards successful GEP implementation in HEIs may act as paradigms for effective mainstreaming gender equality and inclusiveness in HEIs either as success stories or as avoidance examples. To this end, the present document presents also a validated methodology for documenting applied strategies as *Best Practices for mainstreaming Gender Equality and Inclusive Education in HEIs* along with more or less successful examples.

2. Gender Equality at EU and National level

2.1. Overview of gender equality

According to the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)⁷, **Gender Equality** refers to equal rights, responsibilities, and opportunities for all individuals, regardless of their gender. This includes equal access to education, healthcare, and economic opportunities, as well as the ability to live free from gender bias and discrimination. In this context, gender mainstreaming has been internationally adopted as a key strategy towards making gender equality a reality.

Goal 5 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is "Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls by 2030."

This goal has several targets, including:

- Eliminating all forms of discrimination against women and girls
- Eliminating violence against women and girls
- Eliminating harmful practices, such as child marriage and female genital mutilation/cutting
- Recognizing and valuing the unpaid care and domestic work of women and girls
- Ensuring women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic, and public life
- Ensuring universal access to sexual and reproductive health and rights
- Enhancing the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communication technology, to promote the empowerment of women.

Working towards the targets of Goal 5, a world where everyone shares equal opportunities to reach their full potential regardless of their gender, will be created. After all, gender equality acknowledges that individuals may have different needs and experiences based on their gender, and it strives to address these differences in a way that promotes fairness and equality for all.

⁷ https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1059?language_content_entity=en

Figure 1: The conceptual framework of EIGE Gender Equality Index with the domains and sub-domains contributing to the Gender Equality

The [Gender Equality Index](#) developed by EIGE, is a tool to measure the progress of gender equality in several areas of economic and social life adopted by the EU and its Member States. These areas are summarized into a circular structure of domains and sub-domains (**Fig. 1**). Thus, Gender Equality Index represents an aggregate indicator that enables the measurement of the complex concept of gender equality. It is rooted in a gender perspective that reflects the most important areas of EU policy and is conceptually shaped to be based on the view that gender equality contributes to the

transformation of societies. Hence, the values of the index primarily reflect the gender gap, and not the specific status of women and men individually. Advancement of gender equality and empowerment of women and girls towards a more equitable and inclusive society for all have many dimensions and there are numerous strategies towards these achievements.

2.2. Strategies to advance gender equality

- ❖ **Redefining Masculinity and Femininity: Breaking Free from Traditional Gender Roles and Expectations:** Traditional gender roles and expectations (stereotypes) can limit both men and women, preventing them from fully expressing themselves and reaching their full potential. To break free from these constraints, it is important to challenge traditional gender roles and expectations and recognize that both men and women are capable of a wide range of emotions, behaviors, and activities.

In this context, redefining masculinity and femininity is not about eliminating differences between men and women but rather about recognizing that individuals of all genders are complex and multifaceted and should be allowed to express

themselves in a variety of ways. Promoting a more nuanced and inclusive understanding of gender will eventually create a more equitable and acceptable society.

- ❖ *Sharing Household Chores and Childcare Equally:* About 91 % of women with children spend at least an hour per day on housework, compared to 30 % of men with children. Data from the EIGE-2024 Gender Equality Index 2024 Report for Greece shows that the gender gap in unpaid care work has not changed in the last year. That is, despite the proportion of men caring for their children, grandchildren, older people, or people with disabilities increased from 12 % to 30 % between 2007 and 2022, women (37 %) still take on most care work. The gender gap, which has narrowed by 22 pp since 2007, has remained unchanged since 2021. In 2022, in couples with children, 69 % of mothers take on the bulk of care work versus 47 % of fathers. On the other hand, Serbia, a candidate country for EU membership, was the first country outside the European Union to launch a Gender Equality Index back in 2016. Serbia scored 52.4 points in 2016, 55.8 in 2018, and 58.0 in 2021. In the subdomain of household chores and childcare women (67.9%) still bear the brunt and only 11.5% of men cook and/or do household chores every day.

Overall, studies have consistently shown that women bear a disproportionate burden of unpaid care work, including household chores and childcare, while men often do less in these areas.

This gender gap in housework participation can have negative consequences for both men and women. For women, it can limit their opportunities and prevent them from fully participating in the workforce, contributing to overall gender inequality. For men, it can limit their opportunities to develop nurturing and caregiving skills and may reinforce traditional gender roles and expectations. To address this problem, it is important to perform mentality's and cultural change so as to promote the sharing of household chores and childcare tasks to equally between men and women. This could involve creating a plan for dividing up these responsibilities and seeking outside support (affordable childcare and eldercare facilities) to ease the burden.

- ❖ *Encourage Flexible Work Arrangements:* In 2019, a [FlexJobs survey](#), presented that roughly 31% of women who took a career break after having children was due to a lack of workplace flexibility. By offering flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting or part-time work, businesses and companies can support women who are juggling the demands of both work and caregiving and help to promote gender equality and women's economic empowerment.
- ❖ *Advocate for Paid Family Leave:* Paid family leave, which provides employees with paid time off to care for a new child or a sick family member, is an important policy for promoting gender balance and equal rights with several benefits, including:
 - Improved health outcomes for new mothers and infants
 - Increased bonding between parents and children
 - Improved mental health and well-being for caregivers
 - Increased gender equality, as paid family leave allows both men and women to take time off work to care for a new child or a sick family member

However, access to this policy is still limited in many countries, particularly in key roles and industries. To address these gender issues and make paid family leave more widely available, it is important to advocate for policies that support this benefit. It is also important to recognize that paid family leave is not just a "women's issue" but rather a policy that benefits both men and women and helps promote gender balance and equal rights.

- ❖ *Promote Equal Pay:* According to the [International Labor Organization](#) women are paid about 20% less than men on average, globally. Addressing the gender pay gap presents several benefits including,
 - Improved economic opportunities for women: By closing the pay gap, women can have more financial independence and be better able to pursue their own goals and aspirations.

- Stronger families and communities: Equal pay can help to create more balanced and equitable relationships between men and women, which can, in turn, lead to stronger families and communities.

In the EU, the [EU Pay Transparency Directive](#) is set to transform workplace equality, requiring companies to disclose pay structures and address unjustified gender pay gaps. Besides the Pay Transparency Directive there are a number of other measures that can be taken to promote equal pay, including negotiating for higher pay, advocating for pay transparency, and supporting policies that promote equal pay

- ❖ *Identifying and Responding to the Signs of Domestic Violence*: Around 50 million women aged 18-74 in the EU, or 31%, experienced physical (including threats) or sexual violence in adulthood, based on the EU gender-based violence survey ([wave 2021](#)). In addition, 1 in 8 women have experienced sexual violence, including rape, by a non-partner. When comparing the prevalence of gender-based violence by age group, 35% of women in the youngest age group (aged 18 to 29) reported experiencing gender-based violence, compared with 24% in the oldest age group (aged 65-74). Data also show that home is not always a safe place for many women. In 2021, 18% of women who had ever had a partner experienced physical or sexual violence by their partner, and if psychological violence is also taken into account, 32% have or have had a violent partner in their lifetime. Domestic violence is a major barrier to gender equality and women's equality. This type of violence, which refers to physical, sexual assault, or emotional abuse by a current or former partner, affects women in all countries. But it is particularly prevalent in low-income countries. Despite the efforts of organizations and individuals working to combat violence against women, it remains a persistent issue that needs to be addressed.

Intimate partner violence can have a number of negative consequences for women, including physical and mental health problems, economic insecurity, and HIV. In many countries, the highest levels of intimate partner violence are experienced by women in their reproductive years, highlighting the intersection of gender-based violence and women's reproductive health. To address the problem of intimate partner violence and promote gender equality, it is important for national

governments to adopt approaches that aim to prevent this type of violence and provide support to survivors. In addition, it is important to support policies and programs that aim to prevent this type of violence. This can include initiatives such as hotlines, shelters, and legal assistance.

❖ *Promote Inclusive Leadership:* Gender bias can be a significant barrier to inclusive leadership and to the promotion of women leaders into leadership positions. Globally, women hold just 24% of senior leadership positions. According to the

[Federal Statistical Office](#), around 46 % of all employees in the EU were women in 2022. At just 35.1 % (Fig. 2), only one in three managers was female that year. Women are therefore significantly underrepresented at management level.

Figure 2: Proportion of women in management positions in 2022 in Europe, [Federal Statistical Office](#)

and includes women and other underrepresented groups, can have a number of benefits for organizations, including:

- **Improved decision making:** Research has shown that diverse groups tend to make better decisions, as they are more likely to consider a wider range of perspectives and ideas.
- **Enhanced creativity and innovation:** Diversity can stimulate new ideas and approaches, leading to increased creativity and innovation.

- Greater representation: Inclusive leadership can help to ensure that the experiences and needs of all members of the organization are considered and valued.

There are a number of strategies that organizations can use to promote more inclusive leadership, such as:

- Removing gender bias in interviews: This can help to remove gender considerations when selecting candidates for leadership positions. Train interviewers on unconscious bias to promote more objective and fair decision-making, use structured interviews, and use diverse interview panels.
- Providing leadership development opportunities: Organizations can invest in leadership development programs that focus on diversity and inclusion and that provide opportunities for women to gain the skills and experience needed to become leaders.
- Developing brief interventions: Simple interventions, such as providing women with information about their own performance or encouraging them to apply for leadership roles, can help to promote more inclusive leadership.
- ❖ *Encourage Men to Be Allies*: Men can play a vital role in the fight for gender equality by acting as allies and supporting and advocating for women. There are a number of ways that men can be allies in this effort, including:
 - Educating themselves: Men can educate themselves about gender issues and the experiences of women by reading books and articles, attending workshops and seminars, and engaging in discussions with women and other men.
 - Speaking up: Men can speak up and challenge gender stereotypes and biases when they see them, whether in the workplace or their personal lives. This can involve calling out inappropriate comments or behaviors and supporting women who speak out about these issues.

- Supporting women's leadership: Men can support women's leadership by actively seeking out and promoting women for leadership positions and by providing mentorship and guidance to women.
 - Donating time and resources: Men can also donate their time and resources to organizations and initiatives that support gender equality, such as women's shelters, mentorship programs, and advocacy groups.
 - Being a role model: Men can also be role models for other men and boys by modeling respectful and inclusive behavior and by challenging traditional gender roles and expectations.
- ❖ *Address Discrimination and Harassment*: Discrimination and harassment can significantly impact both individuals and organizations, creating an unwelcoming and disrespectful environment. It is essential for organizations to take steps to address discrimination and harassment and to create a more welcoming and respectful workplace. Some strategies for addressing discrimination and harassment include:
- Implementing policies and procedures: Developing and implementing policies that clearly outline what is and is not acceptable can help to create a more respectful workplace. These policies should be communicated to all employees and should be consistently enforced.
 - Providing training: Provide training on diversity and inclusion, as well as on how to recognize and report discrimination and harassment.
 - Encouraging reporting: Encouraging employees to report incidents of discrimination and harassment can help to create a more open and inclusive workplace. It is important for organizations to have a clear process in place for handling such reports and to take all reports seriously.
 - Promoting a culture of respect: Organizations can also promote a culture of respect by modeling inclusive and respectful behavior and by recognizing and rewarding employees who exhibit such behavior.

- ❖ *The Role of Foreign Policy in Advancing Gender Equality:* Feminist foreign policies are foreign policies that prioritize gender equality and the promotion of women's rights. They often seek to address the ways in which traditional foreign policy approaches have excluded or marginalized women and to incorporate a gender perspective into all aspects of foreign policy decision-making.

Feminist foreign policies can have a positive impact on human rights and women's rights in a number of ways. For example, by prioritizing gender equality and women's empowerment, feminist foreign policies can help to address and prevent gender-based violence and discrimination. They can also support the development of laws and policies that promote gender equality and women's rights and increase the participation of women in political, economic, and social spheres. In addition, feminist foreign policies can help to raise awareness and understanding of the ways in which gender inequality and the subordination of women are linked to other issues, such as conflict, poverty, and economic development. By addressing these interconnected issues, feminist foreign policies can help to create more just and equitable societies.

Why Gender Inequality Affects Everyone

In countries with greater gender inequality, simply closing the gap in women's labor force participation could increase economic output by an average of 35%. Gender inequality is not just a women's issue, it affects everyone. It is a fundamental human rights violation and a barrier to achieving [Sustainable Development Goals](#). Men and women should be equal partners in society, yet this is often not the case. The fact that gender remains one of the most consistent indicators of inequality worldwide is a reflection of the deep-seated power imbalances that continue to exist. It has to be acknowledged that these imbalances have consequences, not just for women but for all people.

To truly achieve gender equality, EU citizens must commit themselves to dismantling the systems of oppression that perpetuate these imbalances. This requires a multifaceted approach that includes changing societal attitudes, strengthening national laws and policies, and ensuring that women's rights are protected and promoted at all

levels. Gender equality is not just a matter of justice and human rights; it is also a matter of practicality and common sense. Only equal opportunities to reach full potential for everyone may pave the way to an equitable and sustainable future for all.

2.3 Gender Equality in TALLHEDA widening countries

In 2024, the average Gender Equality Index score for the European Union is 71 out of 100 points, constituting an incremental almost 1-point increase on the 2023 Index score and an increase of 7.9 points in total since 2010. The upward convergence in gender equality describes increasing equality between women and men in the EU is accompanied by a decline in variations between Member States. This means that countries with lower levels of gender equality are catching up with those with the highest levels, thereby reducing disparities across the EU. Analysis of convergence patterns in the Gender Equality Index shows that disparities between Member States decreased over the period 2010-2022, and that *EU Member States endure their trend of upward convergence*.

2.3.1 GREECE

Among EU Member States, Greece ranks 25th in 2024 with a total Gender Equality Index score of 59.3 out of 100 (11.7 points below EU average score)⁸. Furthermore, between 2021 to 2022, Greece recorded one of the largest increases among Member States, having the opportunity to climbing three places in the overall ranking. This was due to the cumulative improvement in Gender Equality Index domains of time ($\geq +31$ points), power ($\geq +13.7$ points) between 2010 to 2022 and currently money ($\sim +2$ points) between 2020 to 2022 and the recent drop by one position in this year's edition of the Index was due to faster progress in other Member States⁹. Interestingly, Greece excels in the domain of health status, scoring 94.6 points and ranking 4th among all Member States, an improvement of two positions in the overall EU ranking as recoded in the 2024 Index report. The biggest improvement was recorded in the domain of power, with an increase of

⁸ GENDER EQUALITY INDEX 2024 Sustaining momentum on a fragile path doi:10.2839/9523460 https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/publications/gender-equality-index-2024-sustaining-momentum-fragile-path?language_content_entity=en

⁹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2024/EL>

2.8 points, elevating the country's ranking from 24th to 22nd place. All sub-domains of the domain of power increased, with the most substantial gain in economic power, which has increased by 6.7 points since 2021 and by 23.8 points since 2010. However, gender inequalities remain highly pronounced in the domain of work in Greece. With a score of 69.4 points, Greece ranks 24th in this domain, its lowest ranking. Since 2010, Greece has improved its position in this domain by two places, with a slight increase of 0.7 points since 2021. Greece has shown an increase in the sub-domain of participation, rising by 1.9 points since 2021. However, the sub-domain of segregation and quality of work has seen a slight decline, dropping by 0.3 points since 2021. Furthermore, *despite a notable increase in the knowledge domain since 2010 (+ 4.3 points), Greece remains among the lowest-ranked countries in this domain, standing at 23rd place.*

2.3.2 SERBIA

Serbia is an EU Associated Country with the accession negotiations for its EU full membership opening back in 2013. Among countries outside EU, Serbia is the first to introduce the Gender Equality Index as early as 2016 with the last updated version launched in 2021¹⁰. Serbia scored 52.4 points in 2016, 55.8 in 2018, and 58.0 in 2021. This indicates continuous, albeit slow progress in improving gender equality that is anticipated to increase since in 2021 Serbia adopted the EU Law on Gender Equality along with the amendments to the EU Law on the Prohibition of Discrimination. Furthermore, the 2021 Index edition revealed the biggest improvement in the domain of power, where an increase of 18.5 points was recorded since the first edition of 2016. Other domains, namely work, money and health, presented a slower rate of improvement (2.1, 0.6 and 0.7 points, respectively). Furthermore, Serbia has a lower index for the domain of knowledge than the EU-27 by 6.8 points. Regarding sub-domains, the gap is significantly larger in the field of educational attainment and participation. That is, for example, the share of highly educated women in 2018 in Estonia was 44.0%, in Sweden 41.7%, in

¹⁰ https://eige.europa.eu/about/eu-candidate-countries-and-potential-candidates/serbia?language_content_entity=en

Slovenia 28.7%, while in Serbia it was 20.3%. Interestingly, *the score in the domain of knowledge in Serbia has decreased (-0.9 points) since 2016.*

3. Gender Equality in Higher Education

3.1. *Overview of Gender Equality in Higher Education - the benefits and the relevance to the EU policy era*

Education, via increasing cognitive and non-cognitive skills and knowledge, contributes to improving productivity and provides individuals with a greater ability to further develop their knowledge and skills throughout their lives. In this context, education is considered a catalyst for social change and a condition for the achievement of fundamental human rights, including gender equality. Furthermore, it ensures that all citizens are better equipped to secure steady, well-paid jobs and thus combat the risks of social exclusion and poverty. In addition, education is the channel through which both women and men are better prepared to timely recognize and handle difficult situations. That is, for example, economic independence makes it easier to leave a difficult situation, such as domestic violence. At the same time, educated citizens benefit entire societies. They make substantial contributions to the economy and contribute to improved health, nutrition and education of their families.

In education, **gender equality** means that girls and boys, men and women, have the same opportunities to receive education, with the same resources, and with the same expectations of success in completing their studies and in labor market. Gender equality in all levels of education also means that **the education system is inclusive**, responsive, and empowering for all students, regardless of their gender.

In this context, **inclusive education** plays a crucial role in promoting gender equality both in education and in society. It is a powerful tool that can help break down gender stereotypes and empower women and girls to reach their full potential. For example, findings from the [World Bank](#) indicate that when girls have access to education, they are more likely to become leaders in their communities, start their own businesses, and make informed decisions about their health and well-being.

Furthermore, girls' education goes beyond getting girls into school. It is also about ensuring that girls feel safe while in school; have the opportunity to complete all levels of education, acquiring the knowledge and skills to compete in the labor market; gain socio-emotional and life skills necessary to navigate and adapt to a changing world; make decisions about their own lives; and contribute to their communities and the world. Especially empowering young women for attending higher levels of education (i.e. MSc or PhD) may also offer added value in research and innovation and HEIs are considered as R&I incubators. Mainstreaming gender equality in education and training policy remains crucial even in countries where equal access to education is taken as a given, which is the actual case in the majority of EU Member States. That is, indicators of social inclusion, employment rates, and job quality reveal that women face an increased risk of social exclusion, unemployment and low-quality and payment jobs compared to men with the same level of education in EU¹¹¹². This is in sharp contrast with the overall higher success rates of girls and women in the EU in terms of completing school education, accessing higher education or participating in lifelong learning¹³, which would be anticipated to being translated into more women in better jobs. This is a stark reminder of the importance of equality in relationships and how it begins with equal access to attend and complete education for both genders. In the same lines, EIGE supports that reducing the aforementioned gender imbalances predisposes challenging and deconstructing gender prejudices and stereotypes throughout the education cycle, from primary school to lifelong learning.

The Benefits of Investing in Gender Equality in Higher Education

Girls' education, alongside improved sexual and reproductive health and rights, has often been cited as the world's best investment. That is, gender equality in education is not only important for empowering girls and women but also has a positive impact on macroeconomic and financial stability. Gender equality in higher education can stimulate economic growth by increasing the number of educated and skilled workers

¹¹ European Commission Expert Group on Gender, Social Inclusion and Employment, *Gender inequalities in the risks of poverty and social exclusion for disadvantaged groups in thirty European countries*, Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Luxembourg, 2009, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/640e54fe-023d-4725-9efe-b3c73e08491e>.

¹² Eurostat/Eurydice, *Key data on education in Europe 2012*, Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency, 2012, Brussels, <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/publications/key-data-education-europe-2012>

¹³ [Key Data on Education in Europe 2012](#)

in the labor force. In turn, this can lead to higher productivity and innovation. Additionally, having more women in leadership positions in the private and public sector can boost performance by increasing diversity and promoting better decision-making.

Investing in gender equality in education has numerous benefits for both individuals and society as a whole.

- ❖ *Education as a tool for breaking down gender stereotypes:* Gender stereotypes are often reinforced through the education system, which can limit the aspirations and opportunities of girls and boys. Quality education that is inclusive and responsive to the diverse needs of all learners can help to break down these stereotypes and promote gender equity. By providing girls and boys with the same opportunities and resources to succeed, the education system can help to address the gender gap in education and promote gender equality.
- ❖ *Education as a means of empowering women and girls:* Girl's education is one of the best ways to empower women and girls and help them to reach their full potential. Educated girls are more likely to have better paying jobs and contribute to the economy. This in turn can lead to reduced poverty and increased economic growth.
- ❖ *Education is an important tool in addressing gender-based violence:* Education can help to reduce the risk of gender-based violence and promote gender equality in other areas of life. By providing girls and boys with education on healthy relationships and gender equality, the education system can help to reduce the risk of gender-based violence. School-based programs that address gender-based violence can also provide support and resources for students who have experienced violence and promote a safer and more inclusive learning environment for all students.
- ❖ *Education has a multigenerational impact:* Investing in girls' education can have a positive impact on multiple generations. Educated girls are more likely to educate their own children, breaking the cycle of poverty and inequality.

- ❖ *Gender equality in education increases social and political participation:* Educated girls are more likely to be active and informed citizens, and to participate in social and political activities.
- ❖ *Gender equality in education presents macroeconomic added value:* A [EIGE study](#), utilizing the empirical E3ME macroeconomic model to estimate the economic impacts of improvements in gender equality tailored specifically to model outcomes at EU and Member State levels, showed that gender equality measures such as the removal of gender stereotypes in education; awareness raising and the promotion of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) subjects¹⁴ to girls and women; and career guidance to encourage girls to consider studying in fields dominated by men and boys in ones dominated by women are likely to result in higher number of women graduating from STEM subjects. Closing gender gaps in STEM education would have a positive impact on employment. Total EU employment would rise by 850.000 to 1.200.000 by 2050. These jobs are forecasted mostly in the long term, as employment rates will rise only after more women studying STEM finish their education. The new jobs are likely to be highly productive because women graduating from STEM often progress into high-added-value positions in sectors such as information and communication or financial and business services. Increasing the participation of women in STEM subjects will have a strong positive GDP impact at EU level. According to the EIGE study, closing the gender gap in STEM would contribute to an increase in EU GDP per capita by 0.7-0.9 % in 2030. By 2050, the increase is forecasted for 2.2 % and 3.0 %. In monetary terms, closing the STEM gap leads to an improvement in GDP by EUR 610-820 billion in 2050. Furthermore, improved on average gender equality in EU member states is expected to lead to an increase in GDP of about 12% by 2050¹⁵.
- ❖ *Research and Innovation benefits:* Gender equality in EU research and innovation (R&I) offers significant benefits, including increased research quality, improved

¹⁴ STEM definition is according to the UNESCO classification. That is, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields are coded as 05 (natural sciences, mathematics and statistics), 06 (information and communication technologies) and 07 (engineering, manufacturing and construction) in ISCED-F 2013.

¹⁵ <https://eige.europa.eu/newsroom/economic-benefits-gender-equality>

talent attraction and retention, and a more inclusive and equitable work environment. By ensuring that everyone can contribute to their potential, gender equality enhances the overall quality and relevance of R&I.

More specifically it 1) improves Research Quality: Gender-diverse teams bring a broader range of perspectives, leading to more creative and innovative solutions, which in turn enhances the quality of research. Integrating a gender dimension into R&I content improves research design, hypotheses, and protocols, ultimately leading to more valid and reliable results; 2) attracts and retains talent: A commitment to gender equality creates a more inclusive and welcoming environment, attracting and retaining top-tier researchers and innovators. This leads to increased productivity, innovation, and overall economic output; 3) provides economic benefits: Gender equality contributes to a more skilled and competitive workforce, leading to increased economic growth. Closing the gender gap in STEM fields could lead to a significant increase in EU GDP per capita and employment rates; 4) provides fairness and inclusiveness: Gender equality ensures that everyone has the opportunity to contribute their skills and talents, fostering a more equitable and inclusive research environment; 5) provides Social and Ethical Benefits: Gender equality is a fundamental human right and a key component of a healthy and sustainable society; 6) presents compliance with regulations: Promoting gender equality in R&I helps research organizations comply with domestic and European Union regulations; 7) contributes to leverage for organizational change: Implementing gender equality initiatives requires a broad effort involving all staff categories, leading to a more flexible, creative, and sustainable working culture.

3.2. Obstacles to gender equality in Higher Education

Gender equality in accessing and completing higher education and life-long training continues to be affected by several factors and the role of both biological differences and environmental conditions have been included in the present document. These factors include educational context, family environment and role models (stereotypes), behavioral and psychological factors, preferences and culture all of which contribute to several challenges that gender equality and inclusive education face, such as:

- ***Gender-based different choices across schooling systems and study fields.***
Gender segregation in the labor market as a result of different educational and professional choices in schools and universities, for pupils, students and teachers, is widespread. The characteristics of schooling systems, their institutional set-up, the design of curricula, resources, teachers and peers play important roles in creating the educational context that has been strongly correlated with long-lasting effects over the higher educational preferences and professional life cycle for both genders. Schooling systems in EU vary between the comprehensive education and the tracking system of education. The tracking system refers to the practice of sorting students into different streams/schools (e.g. general education vs VET) according to their ability, at an early age (typically around age 10) and is favored in countries with greater emphasis on apprenticeship like Germany, Denmark and Switzerland. On the other hand, the comprehensive educational system, by contrast, provides multidiscipline and wide-ranging education to all children universally. It has been shown that early tracking systems increase and widen the inequality in educational achievement, though the evidence is less conclusive regarding their negative effect on the level of performance¹⁶.

More importantly, different choices across study fields between women and men is still a relevant characteristic of gender differences in education patterns in the EU-28. According to the [EU Education and Training Monitor 2024 comparative report](#), the share of people 25-30-years-old with tertiary education attainment was 43.1% at 2023, up 1.1 p.p. from the previous year. Among them, a master's degree is the most common educational level attained (19.2%) closely followed by a bachelor's degree (18.8%). Only 4.5% of young adults (25-34) have a short-cycle degree and fewer than 1% (0.7%) of 25-34-year-olds have a doctorate. Looking at the long-term trend since 2014, the rate has increased in virtually all countries and by more than 7.2 p.p. at an average EU level. Gender differences are, however, substantial. That is, women are still severely under-represented in science, technology, engineering

¹⁶ Hanushek, E.A. and Wössmann, L. 2006. "Does Educational Tracking Affect Performance and Inequality? Differences-in-Differences Evidence Across Countries." *Economic Journal* 116 (510): 63-76.

and mathematics fields (STEM)¹⁷. This is due mostly, out of all male new entrants, 9.0% chose ICT programs in 2022, compared to 1.9% of women. The gender gap is less pronounced in the other two STEM areas: women represent 52.0% of new entrants to natural sciences, mathematics, and statistics; and 26.3% of new entrants to engineering, manufacturing, and construction. Women make up the majority of tertiary graduates in all EU countries, but in ICT, only one in five (21.3%) graduates is a woman. New female entrants to ICT programs represent 20.2% of ICT entrants - and the share has increased by only 1.6 p.p since 2016 - leaving ICT dominated by men. Female shares are higher for engineering, manufacturing, and construction (27.7%) and natural sciences, mathematics, and statistics (59.7%). One of the reasons for this situation is the persistent labelling of study areas and work as either 'feminine' or 'masculine'. According to the [2024 European Commission report](#) on how to address the gender gap in STEM higher education, a systematic identification and analysis of the factors at individual, contextual and institutional levels that contribute to the gender gap in STEM education is needed. These factors include societal attitudes, educational context, curriculum design and the role of educators in shaping gender perceptions and choices in STEM. The particular issue calls for a comprehensive, multi-level approach that encompasses educational reforms, policy interventions, societal attitude shifts and targeted support mechanisms to bridge this gap effectively. Addressing the gender gap in STEM is not only a matter of educational equity but also an issue of critical economic and societal concern, given the increasing importance of STEM fields in navigating the modern world, driving innovation, and addressing global challenges. In accordance to aforementioned EU report, the Indicators of the forum Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development ([OECD Indicators](#)), also support that gender differences in student performance, as well as perceptions that some fields of education are more 'suitable' for either women or men, need to be addressed if greater gender equity in education outcomes is to be achieved.

¹⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/33c86740-cd54-11ea-adf7-01aa75ed71a1>

In the same context, it has been shown that labor market conditions of specific occupations (such as expected earnings, career progression, workplace flexibility and job security) may affect previous decisions in education. That is males prefer jobs with higher growth rates in earnings while females prefer more secure jobs and jobs with greater flexibility. In the Wiswall and Jafar (2018)¹⁸ study, the authors showed that for a university major, one standard deviation increase in the perceived probability of dismissal in future jobs drives 5% of women and 4% of men away from a major, and one standard deviation increase in the perceived average earnings from future jobs attracts 5% more women and 16% more men to a major.

Cultural beliefs and practices may further enhance gender inequalities in educational and professional choices in HEIs. That is, specific socio-economic populations belonging to minority ethno-linguistic groups (i.e. Roma, refugees etc.) present several divergences from the general European population in gender equality in all levels of education mostly due to cultural beliefs and practices that promote or even impose specific feminine academic study fields for young women compatible to their domestic responsibilities and work.

- ***Gender stereotypes in higher education.*** Gender stereotypes refer to a set of socially and culturally constructed beliefs about what it means to be female and /or male and occurs when a person is expected to enact a series of gender-based norms or behaviors. In the area of higher education and training, sexist stereotypes are reinforced by both the teachers that may utilize sexist language in educational settings and the teaching materials (i.e. textbooks containing many stereotypes that provide examples through gendered images diminishing the role of women especially the case when men and women are depicted in professional contexts). The consequences have been determined by EIGE which ascertained that gender structural inequalities are deeply entrenched in the history of each discipline. Indeed, the [EU Education and Training Monitor 2024 comparative report](#) and the [EENEE, 2021 report](#) “*Gender Gaps in Education: Evidence and Policy Information*”

¹⁸ Wiswall, M., and Zafar, B. 2018. “Preference for the Workplace, Investment in Human Capital, and Gender.” Quarterly Journal of Economics 133 (1): 457-507.

revealed that the gender gap among the doctorate holders is much lower than at the bachelor's level and is actually very small or even not significant for most EU member states. However, there are significant gender inequalities by field of study: women are on average over-represented in fields of health, welfare, arts, humanities, social sciences and journalism and are under-represented in STEM. EENEE findings showed that this pattern is consistent at all levels and increases with the level of educational achievement. Gender stereotypes in education may be further reinforced by social and cultural norms. That is, societies with higher levels of gender equity present smaller gaps in academic achievement¹⁹.

- **Gender and lifelong training.** Acknowledging that a competitive and knowledge-based economy for Europe requires continuous training as a key ingredient towards economic and social development and resilience, gender equality in lifelong training is a necessity. Constant technological advances require workers to continuously upskill and keep abreast of new developments during their careers. Lifelong learning is also instrumental in women's reintegration into the labor market following a career break due to care responsibilities. Thus, lifelong education and training can be a catalyst for greater gender equality provided both women and men can access it despite work and family constraints. However, lack of time or financial resources can significantly hamper access to adult learning and training and inhibit certain groups of women and men more than others. In 2017, the EU-28 average of women and men aged 25-64 years participating in education and training was 12 % and 10 % respectively, well below the Europe 2020 target. The gender gap of 2 p.p. in favor of women was evident among 25-49-year-olds, and it remained the same among women and men aged 50-64 years, despite overall participation in education and training sharply decreasing as people approach retirement²⁰. The EU trend followed similar lines among those in or out of work: 13% of employed women and 10% of employed men were engaged in education and training; among unemployed people,

¹⁹ Gevrek, Z.E., Gevrek, D., and Neumeier, C. 2020. "Explaining the gender gaps in mathematics achievement and attitudes: The role of societal gender equality." *Economics of Education Review* 76: 101978.

²⁰ EIGE's calculation, Eurostat, European Union Labour Force Survey (trng_lfs_01).

it was 11% of women and 9% of men²¹. Overall, in a rapidly changing knowledge economy, continuous learning throughout life is essential for both women and men but finding the time to maintain and increase skills and knowledge is challenging. As women and men tend to face different time-related barriers to lifelong learning, better work–life policies would not only allow a more satisfactory combination of job and family responsibilities, but they would also free up time for continuous investment and growth in people’s skills and knowledge.

- ***Gender imbalances in academic positions: the feminization of low-to-intermediate teaching positions versus the masculinization of higher teaching position in tertiary education.*** According to the [2021 European Commission report](#) on girls’ career aspiration in STEM, based on the in-depth descriptive and econometric analysis of [OECD PISA 2018 microdata](#), women are running behind in the labor market for science and technology. They are rather overrepresented as teachers at the levels of primary and secondary education while they are still lacking behind as higher education professors. Increasing the proportion of women in STEM, is important to expanding the labor force in science and technology (ICT), to increasing women’s access to well-paid jobs, and promoting the development of technology that is not gender biased. Furthermore, the essence of an academic professor prerequisites, beyond teaching, and the research dimension. In this context, gender segregation in research is a persistent issue despite the efforts made and are still making to change the trends of male and female choices in the study fields. Interestingly, the EU [She Figures 2021](#) report revealed some positive trends, with almost gender parity at PhD graduate level and a slight increase in the proportion of women holding the highest academic positions (26.2%) compared to the last edition (24.1%). However, when looking at the representation of women doctoral graduates in specific fields of study, such as Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction, these numbers remain as low as 22.4% and 30%, respectively. The lack of women in these fields translates into biased R&I output, loss of talent and growth

²¹ Eurostat, Education statistics, 2017 (trng_lfs_03).

opportunities. That is, data also show that horizontal segregation persists in research careers across the main economic sectors (higher education, government and business), with a higher percentage of women researchers being employed in the higher education sector (55.9%). In comparison, men researchers are more likely to be employed in the business enterprise sector (53.3%). Horizontal gender segregation also persists across the different fields of Research and Development (R&D). At country level, men were more likely than women to work as researchers in Natural Sciences and Engineering & Technology in most countries for all economic sectors considered. Furthermore, comparison of women's and men's representation in different grades of an academic career and in decision-making positions showed that at European level in 2018, women represented more than 40% of academic staff. However, there were considerable differences by grade creating the “sticky floor” phenomenon to describe the difficulty faced by women scholars in moving up the career ladder after gaining low-to-intermediate positions. That is, while women represented nearly half of grade C and D staff (46.6% of grade C staff and 47.1% of grade D staff) and more than 40% of grade B staff (40.3%), they only occupied around a quarter of grade A staff positions (26.2%) - equivalent to full professorship. It was also found that, in each and every field of Research and Development, women represented no more than around one-third of grade A staff at European level in 2018. In addition, despite several EU policies, such as the [Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025](#) emphasizing the importance of increasing women's representation in leadership positions, the proportion of women as heads of institutions in the higher education sector in 2019 stood at only 23.6%. Also, at European level in 2019, just over 3 in 10 board members were women (31.1%) and under one-quarter of board leaders (24.5%) were women creating, thus, the “glass ceiling” phenomenon to describe the lack of women in top managerial or scientific positions and the underlined obstacles and inequalities that contribute to this situation. In conclusion, it is obvious that women are over-represented in relatively low-to-intermediate academic positions whereas men dominate in higher-status and better-paid positions that hold greater influence in policy- and decision-making.

- **Gender inequalities in research and innovation.** Equality in research and innovation is a core value of the European Union, essential for fostering excellence, diversity, and inclusiveness. To monitor gender equality mainstreaming in the European R&I system, [SheFigures Index](#), a tool introduced in [2014 SheFigures report](#), shows that in 2024 the overall Index scores in EU member states range between 60% and 88%. For Greece, the index is configured at 71.4% while for Serbia at 55.5% presenting large room for improvement. For Belgium, the third country involved in TALLHEDA project, the index is 69.9%. The index draws on a range of She Figures indicators across six key dimensions: pipeline segregation, research sectors, career progression, decision-making, research participation, and the incorporation of a gender dimension in research and innovation content (GDRIC). Furthermore, breaking down the total score it is evident that persistent gender inequalities in research include gender segregation in research and innovation; gender-related career challenges and gender imbalance in senior positions in academia; gender gaps in research productivity; gender bias in access to research funding; gender-blind and gender-biased research; gender-blind and gender-biased organizational culture and institutional processes. In the [European Research Area Policy Agenda for 2022-2024](#), the European Commission emphasizes that gender equality will be pursued through promoting institutional change in R&I organizations. *Gender equality plans* (GEPs) are the main policy instrument used to achieve this change. However, it seems that, despite efforts, gender inequalities persist in the R&I system across Europe, with a notable gap between the adoption of policies and strategies at EU and national level, and their implementation at the institutional level. Furthermore, the agenda recommends that gender equality policies need to address intersections with other diversity categories and potential grounds of discrimination, such as ethnicity, disability or sexual orientation. Increasing the inclusiveness of gender equality policies in this regard also means that efforts should be made to ensure the equal implementation of these policies in all Member States and in all R&I sectors.
- **Gender-based violence in HEIs.** [Gender-based violence](#) (GBV) is considered “*any type of harm that is perpetrated against a person or group of people because of their factual or perceived sex, gender, sexual orientation and/or gender identity*”

according to the Council of Europe. Gender-based violence occurs in both private and public sectors, and higher education and research institutions are not an exception, but this issue tends to be underestimated in research organizations and research funding bodies. There is evidence that gender-based violence and sexual harassment are widespread in public institutions and universities, but this is not based on systematically collected data. For this reason, the European Commission has supported initiatives such as [UniSAFE](#) to improve knowledge about the extent of the problem and ways to address it. Recent analyses and reviews carried out in the framework of EU-funded projects on structural change, among others, show that there is an urgent need for action on this problem. Importantly, power imbalances are always a central root cause of violence. Also, gender-based violence commonly intersects with other grounds of oppression. As such, gender-based violence and, for example, racial violence can be closely interconnected. Different grounds of oppression and inequality expose people disproportionately to being subjected to violence. It is therefore paramount to consider the specificity of academia, marked by hierarchical structures that place people at distinctively different levels of power and authority, whereby some enjoy strong statutory protection while others work under precarious contracts and yet others are ‘just’ students. In this complicated context, measures are needed, such as providing information regarding sexual and gender-based harassment and offering attention and support to victims and witnesses of misconduct, with a commitment to putting an end to such behavior. A GEP may consider what measures the organization takes to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment, including behavior that violates any individual’s dignity or that creates an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment. At present, UniSAFE initiative coordinated the implementation of the first survey between January and May 2022, among 46 participating universities and research organizations in 15 countries in Europe to collect measurable evidence on the prevalence of gender-based violence in academia and research (*Fig. 3*). With over 42,000 responses from staff and students, the survey is the largest conducted so far in the European Research Area. The prevalence of gender-based violence is defined as the proportion of respondents who have experienced any form of gender-

based violence asked about in the survey since they started working or studying at their institution. These different forms of gender-based violence consist of physical violence, psychological violence, economic violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, and online violence. The overall results showed that 62% of the survey respondents have experienced at least one form of gender-based violence since they started working or studying at their institution. Almost 1 in 3 respondents (31%) have experienced sexual harassment, whereas 3% have experienced 3% sexual violence. Among the respondents who had experienced gender-based violence, only 13% reported it. Almost half of the victims (47%) explained that they felt uncertain whether the behavior was serious enough to be reported. Another frequent reason indicated by 31% of the victims is that at the time of the incident they did not identify the behavior as an act of violence. Interestingly, only 7% of the students suffered gender-based violence in the context of their institutions have reported it, strongly indicating that there is an urgent need for action on this problem.

3.3. *Tackling gender inequalities in Higher Education*

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are incubators for the thought leaders and social leaders of the future. HEIs and systems where norms for gender equality are practiced and modelled, and where the voices and ideas of women are valued and raised up, are powerful tools for accelerating progress towards the equality and empowerment of women and girls everywhere. However, evidence shows that gender equality issues impact and are reflected in higher education systems worldwide - with unequal access to higher education in many countries, fewer resources and opportunities available to women, the existence of violence against women affecting students and staff, and sustained underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in HEIs. Despite women succeeding academically, it is more challenging for women to succeed in their careers both within and outside academia following their studies although they are excelling in lifelong education and training curricula.

According to the [EU Education and Training Monitor 2024 comparative report](#) and the [EENEE, 2021 report](#) “Gender Gaps in Education: Evidence and Policy Information” in Europe the gender gap in educational attainment has been reversed in tertiary education in the majority of the EU member states. However, remaining issues still exist

Figure 3. Prevalence of any form of gender-based violence and by form of gender-based violence. Data are originated from the UniSAFE Survey on Gender-based violence and institutional responses. <https://doi.org/10.7802/2475>

with the major gender gap being observed across fields of study in STEM. Gender gaps in educational choices emerge early in secondary schooling and widen along the educational trajectory. Existing data indicate that there is a complex set of driving forces, and the resultant force

determines the magnitude of the effects and explains why these effects vary across countries and over time. Among others explanatory factors, the educational context, the structure of labor market and the environment of the workplace along with the social norms and gender equality in cultural values in the family environment seem to share important roles in the final output. In this context, there is a critical need to address gender inequalities in higher education with concerted efforts from governments, higher education oversight and funding bodies, HEIs and other partners. The action requires to transform discriminatory gender norms in higher education - such as unequal domestic burdens falling upon women and bias in assessment, recruitment and promotion - as well as to address the practical barriers that disproportionately affect women because of their place in society should include strategies such as

1. Ensuring an intersectional approach: Best practice is not currently widespread, with the majority of initiatives (i.e. [UniSAFE](#)) taking ‘women’ as the only category of analysis. Efforts and interventions should be inclusive of socio-economically and

culturally minoritized women, disabled women and other disadvantaged groups and consider whether each one gender equality intervention could produce more impact by being targeted at specific groups of women and girls. Most importantly, HEIs, having the ability of being both a working and an educational environment, should develop inclusive strategies for both female students and employees. The different experiences of women and girls with different intersecting identities need to be theorized, monitored and evaluated.

2. Taking a lifecycle approach and act at scale: The impact of any gender equality-transformative interventions is felt over the long term, requiring a long-term approach to planning, monitoring and evaluation. Indicators should go wider than measuring individual success and include multiplier effects such as evidence of participants' ongoing influence in their communities as ambassadors for gender equality. In the same context, the acknowledgement of the linkages between primary, secondary and higher education and employment is considered fundamental to build pathways and opportunities for women and girls, particularly of underfunded and under-represented groups. Higher education curricula will gain only benefits from being linked with and complemented by other curricula of primary or secondary education as well as initiatives of active citizenship and social norms for gender equality in the community. Furthermore, advocacy for gender responsive pedagogy and practice in national and European level should be prioritized, from HEIs' functions to National and European frameworks and partnership programmes that have global reach by incorporating specific GEPs, policies and monitoring systems for enabling transparency and efficacy and best enhancement of the multiplier effects of interventions for gender equality.

3. Put a greater focus on violence against women: GBV in higher education has been identified as an urgent global predicament of unknown magnitude. It is a risk, concern and critical challenge for all those involved in higher education and there is an urgent need to take action for accountability and safeguarding. This requires working with specialists to develop evidence-based policy and assurance frameworks, particularly in transnational HEIs where foreign students appear to be at even greater risk than home students. Communication and guidance should be provided for students and staff. Data

collection on GBV prevalence and institutional response should be mandated. Prevention of GBV in HEIs should be a priority area for investment in best practice.

4. *Strengthen organizational leadership and commitment to address gender equality in strategy, policy, quality assurance and delivery:* Engagement of senior organizational leadership is critical to the advancement of gender equality and inclusive education in HEIs. Decisive ongoing actions to address gender inequalities are needed and should be accompanied by consistent and strong messages about the importance of gender equality and inclusive education agenda promotion. In this context, people in managerial positions should take the lead on gender equality. Male and female leaders should model ‘institutional courage’ in the face of gender inequality by preventing discriminatory actions and omissions (i.e. restricting women’s access to higher education, restricting access to education about gender etc.) as incompatible with core institutional values and communicate this unequivocally to partners, associates and stakeholders working in or with higher education. Training in leadership for gender equality issues should be considered for existing managers and in hiring procedures and qualifications of new managers in higher education.

5. *Tackle subject segregation by gender, particularly in STEM:* STEM remains a priority focus area globally for HEIs, at the same time as being a male-dominated field. This is due mostly under-representation of women in the field of ICT studies whereas significant progress had been made in the subfield of Natural Sciences, Mathematics & Statistics as well as in the subfield of Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction. In this context, when taking action to increase the numbers of women in STEM, it is important to consider STEM subfields of study, country and regional differences to address cultural gendered assumptions and be inclusive of women in all their diversity.

6. *Develop gender expertise:* Gender equality is currently not holistically and comprehensively mainstreamed in EU and associated countries’ HEIs and neither is expertise on gender inequality regularly sought out where it is needed. International NGOs focusing on gender and education, most of the time, do not in higher education spaces. Thus, the HEIs requirement on integrating gender equality considerations into

their working and educational environment, creates a demand for country, regional and global gender specialists who have a specific focus on higher education.

7. Address women's under-representation in higher education leadership: Across the board, women in higher education who are equally as talented as men are deprived of equivalent opportunities to rise to better-rewarded positions of influence and leadership. Women leaders when in place are also notably effective champions of further actions to address other forms of gender inequalities in higher education. HEIs senior administration and staff should commit to long-term actions towards addressing the glass ceiling, sticky floor and other known patterns of impediment to women's equal leadership in higher education, for which there are established good practice models that can be adapted for cultural context as required. Practices and policies for recruitment and promotion, as well as other institutional norms, can conflate good leadership with masculinity, whereas excellence in inclusive leadership should be advanced and rewarded.

8. Assert the centrality of equality and inclusion to the definition of quality and excellence in higher education: Practices that reinforce gender inequalities or that only work well for male population cannot be considered as of high quality. However, evidence supports that quality and excellence in higher education R&I activities are currently reflective of gender inequalities and often perpetuate them. Definitions of quality and excellence in curriculum content, pedagogy, programming, candidate selection and policy must be underpinned by gender equality standards and HEIs curricula - including academic teacher and staff training curricula - should be gender sensitive and compatible with inclusive education.

9. Prioritize gender mainstreaming: Progress towards gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls is a core ambition, but it is not achieved without intentional focus. Gender audits should be conducted systematically, and standard documentation should invite discussion of the ways in which gender analysis is (or is not) relevant to and reflected in HEIs function as a workplace and as an educational environment. Sufficient resource allocation for the work of gender specialists should be factored into planning. Management reviews should include competence and

operational success in gender mainstreaming. Externally commissioned work must include gendered analysis conducted by demonstrably competent analysts. Gender equality objectives and outcomes need to be explicit and not hypothetical or deducted at their documentation. The default indicators in monitoring and evaluation plans should be refined and replaced as necessary, to enable analysis of the gender inequalities and progress towards equality that cannot be captured by simply ‘counting’ participation, access or completion rates by sex/ gender. Layers of disadvantage, including intersecting inequalities, should be identified. Materials demonstrating institutional commitment to gender equality should be developed and promoted in communications.

3.4. Gender Equality and Inclusive education in TALLHEDA widening HEIs

3.4.1 GREECE - A growing number of graduates from tertiary education between both women and men is closing the gender gap and presents a domain Index score of 57.7. Since 2010, the percentage of both women and men with tertiary education has risen, effectively closing the gender gap. In 2022, 26 % of both women and men had graduated from tertiary education, compared to 17 % of women and 18 % of men in 2010. Between 2014 and 2022, the proportion of graduates increased significantly among lone mothers (from 27 % to 46 %) but slightly decreased among lone fathers (from 30 % to 23 %). Gender gaps persist among older people for those aged 65 or more (- 11 pp) and for people with disabilities (- 7 pp), both to the detriment of women. Among people aged 25-49 years, the gender gap favors women, with 7 pp more women having completed tertiary education than men. Younger generations of women are completing higher education at greater rates than both past generations and their male peers. Greek women with ICT higher education and subsequent employment rank high (above EU-average) compared to other EU Members States and associated

Countries including Serbia (Fig. 4), though Greek women occupied in the ICT field is still underrepresented.

Figure 4. Share of employed people with an ICT education by sex, 2023

Notes

- Definitions differ in Spain and in France: see the source data metadata (Labour Force survey - LFS) for more details.
- Men of Iceland: low reliability and not available for publication.
- Women of Croatia, Malta, Austria, Norway, Bosnia and Herzegovina: low reliability.
- Women of Slovenia, Slovakia, Luxembourg, Latvia, Iceland: low reliability and not available for publication.
- Source: Eurostat (online data code: isoc_ski_itsex)

3.4.2 SERBIA - There is a decline in the value of the index for the academic performance and participation sub-domain, as well as the sub-domain of segregation²². That is, in the last updated version of the Gender Equality Index in 2021 the share of persons participating in formal or non-formal education has decreased, both among women and men, and the gender gap has increased compared with results from the 2016 and 2018 version of the Gender Equality Index. Although the share of persons who have obtained a university education among women and men has slightly increased, the gender gap has also slightly increased (from 1.8 points difference to 2.1 between 2018 to 2021), this time in favor of women (with 20.3% of women with tertiary education and 18.2% of men with such education level). Gender segregation by area of

²² https://eige.europa.eu/about/eu-candidate-countries-and-potential-candidates/serbia?language_content_entity=en

education is also on the rise, as measured by the participation of women and men in the areas of education related to health, education, social protection, social sciences, humanities and the arts, contributing mainly to the decrease of Index value for this domain. Furthermore, 28.6% of ICT graduates in Serbia are women, above the EU-27 average (20.5%). Indeed, the number of those enrolled in faculties and post-secondary education in the field of ICT in Serbia was 17% higher in 2019 compared to 2015, the number of enrolled girls is 33% higher, and boys by 11%. However, the higher increase in the number of girls enrolling in post-secondary schools and faculties in the field of ICT compared to the growth in the number of boys resulted in a gender gap decrease of only 3% (girls in 2015 were 26% of those enrolled, in 2019 they represent 29%), indicating the gender segregation in ICT education, despite positive trends, is still highly pronounced. In ICT studies, Serbia is among the better positioned EU countries (a similar percentage is registered by Estonia, Cyprus and Sweden, while only Romania, Bulgaria and Greece have higher values for women than Serbia).

In other STEM areas of education, the share of women in Serbia is higher: women are 71.2% of graduates in natural science, mathematics and statistics, and 38.5% of graduates in engineering, manufacturing and construction, also above the EU average. Women who graduated in the educational field of ICT are interested more in database and network administration, while men are oriented more towards software and application development. Totally, among ICT specialists in Serbia, 21.6% are women, while at the EU-27 level this percentage is lower, at 17.2%, and Serbia registers the highest average annual increase in the number of female ICT specialists in Europe (13% for the period 2011-2019). However, a gender-balanced structure of staff in the ICT sector of Serbia exists only in activities related to information services (data processing, hosting and web portals), while in the field of technology (programming, ICT consulting, management of computer equipment) only one in three employees is a woman (*Fig.4*). Serbian female workers on platforms are better educated than men but earn less. (9.1% less than men), i.e. the gender pay gap in ICT occupations is slightly higher compared to the overall gender pay gap (at the level of all occupations), amounting to 8.8% in Serbia.

4. Best Practices in Gender Equality and Inclusive Education selection

4.1. Definition of Best Practices

Best Practice (or **Good Practice**) is commonly defined as a technique or method that, through experience and research, has proven reliably to lead to the desired result²³. These practices need to be shared and adopted to benefit more people. In the context of higher education (BSc, MSc and PhD studies), a practical definition of a best practice is knowledge about what works in specific situations of Higher Education Institutes (HEIs), without using inordinate resources to achieve the desired results, and which can be used to develop and implement solutions adapted to similar problems in other HEIs. The term best practice has been referred to as **good practices** in literature²⁴ also as by European Institute for Gender Equality ([EIGE](#)). Obviously, the term “best practice” is not about a state of perfection, like being the gold standard or referring to the only elements that have been shown to contribute towards making interventions work or successful²⁵. Most of the time, results are partial and may be related to only one or more components / dimensions of the practice being considered. Indeed, documenting and applying lessons learned on what also does not work and why it does not work are integral parts of a best practice, so that the same types of mistakes can be avoided by others.

4.2. Methodology

4.2.1. Criteria for identifying Best Practices in gender equality and inclusive education in EU HEIs

Taking into consideration that a best practice may involve a relevant policy or intervention, or initiative implemented in a real-life setting, which has been assessed in terms of adequacy, equity, effectiveness and efficiency related to process and outcomes, a set of relevant criteria should be developed in identifying best practices for a particular purpose.

²³ Best practices. In: Bitpipe [website] (<http://www.bitpipe.com/tlist/Best-Practices.html>, accessed 15 February 2017).

²⁴ Ng E, de Colombani P. Framework for selecting best practices in public health: a systematic literature review. *J Public Health Res.* 2015;4(3):577.

²⁵ Best Practice Collection. In: UNAIDS [website] (<http://www.unaids.org/en/site-search?keywords=Best+practice+collection>, accessed 16 February 2017).

These criteria may be divided into three categories:

- ❖ *Inclusion criteria*
- ❖ *Core criteria*
- ❖ *Qualifier criteria*

The *inclusion criteria* involve:

- 1) **Relevance**: in terms of political/strategic context of the practice or intervention or initiative, which needs to be clearly explained and considered. In the present document, selected best practices must address the priority of gender equality and inclusiveness in higher education in EU Member States and Associated countries
- 2) **Intervention characteristics**: in terms of ensuring the existence of a situation analysis, established objectives, a consistent methodology etc.
- 3) **Evidence and theory based**: in terms of scientific excellence or other evidence that have been used, analyzed and disseminated in a conscious, explicit and thoughtful manner.
- 4) **Ethical soundness**: in terms of being respectful of ethical values and personal data and guaranteeing the safeguarding of dignity of human population involved

The *core criteria* involve:

- 1) **Effectiveness** in terms that the practice should work and achieve results that are measurable
- 2) **Efficiency**: the degree to which the practice produced results are reasonable in time and resources consuming. Efficiency provides the measures of which the objectives of quantity, quality and time have been met under real conditions at the lowest possible cost.
- 3) **Equity**: the practice should take into account the needs of the population (men and women) for gender equity in Higher Education when allocating the resources and identify and reduce gender inequalities in HEIs.

The *qualifier criteria* involve:

- 1) **Transferability**: to which extent the implementation of the best practice is systematic and documented, making it possible to transfer it to other contexts/settings/countries or to scale it up to a broader target population/geographic context.
- 2) **Sustainability**: the best practice must be implementable over a long period with the available resources, adapting to social, economic and environmental requirements of the context in which it is developed.
- 3) **Intersectoral coordination and participation**: for ensuring the ability of practice to foster collaboration among the different sectors and stakeholders involved in the domain of interest.
- 4) **Community involvement**: The best practice must involve the participation of the affected communities. In the present document this involves HEIs' faculties, general staff and students.
- 5) **Political commitment**: The best practice must be supported by the relevant local (regional and/or national) authorities

4.2.2. Approach for identifying Gender Equality and Inclusive Education mainstreaming Best Practices

In the topic of Gender Equality and Inclusiveness in Higher Education, the best practices may come from a variety of sources such as

- EU organization and initiatives (EIGE, *SheFigures*, EENEE etc.),
- EU funded projects (i.e. [UniSAFE](#)),
- EU Member States Ministries of Education,
- NGOs and other stakeholders (SMEs, startups etc.), and
- HEIs

For consistency purposes with EU guidelines in documented best practices, this document, requested by TALLHEDA project, will follow the [selection steps of EIGI for best practices in gender equality](#) adjusted for *Best Practices In Gender Equality In Inclusiveness In Higher Education*. These steps are:

1st step: Preparation to

- Identify the **topic**. For the present document the topic is **Gender Equality and Inclusiveness in Research and Academia**
- Identify the **geographical scope**. For the present document, the geographical scope includes **all EU Member States and Associated countries**
- Select specific gender mainstreaming **methods or tools or specific areas/policy priorities**. This involves **gender mainstreaming infrastructure** (2 examples), **competence development** (1 example), **support services** (1 example), **self-regulation** (3 examples) and **benchmarking** (3 examples).

2nd step: Collection and assessment phase to

- collect “practices with potential” fulfilling all basic (inclusion and core) criteria
- identify “promising practices” fulfilling all or most advanced (qualifier) criteria

3rd step: Identification and refinement of best practices

- The **final selection** (identification) of gender equality mainstreaming best practices is carried out in collaboration with stakeholders after presentations on the promising practices by practice owners/implementers, based on a common template, which allows in-depth discussion of the practices and the context in which the practices operate, which might promote or hamper replicability or scalability.
- The **refinement of the identified best practices** on gender equality mainstreaming is carried out in collaboration with practice owners and/or implementers, who add to and validate the information before its publication.

4.2.3. Documentation of Best Practices in Gender Equality and Inclusive Education in HEIs

Gender equality is a core value of the EU. With a score of 71.0 out of 100 in 2024 Gender Equality Index score, the European Union still has a long way to go to achieve gender equality although the current score represents a moderate improvement (+0.8 points) compared to the previous edition of the Index. In this long-term pathway to meet full gender equality, EU and private and public organizations and institutions designed and implemented several methodologies to mainstream gender equality and some of them have been documented as best practices for gender equality after subjected to formal evaluations by EIGE²⁶. **Table 1** presents the outline for the documentation of an initiative as best practice.

Table 1: Outline for documenting Best Practices	
Title of the best practice	The title must be concise and reflect the practice under documentation
Country	
Duration	
Organization	
Contact Person	
Introduction	<p>This section should provide the context of the justification for the practice and address the following</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What was the problem to be addressed? ➤ Which population is affected? ➤ How did the problem impact on the population? ➤ Which objectives were achieved?
Implementation of the practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the main activities carried out? ➤ When and where were the activities carried out? ➤ Who were the key-implementers and collaborators?

²⁶ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices>

Results of the practice outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the concrete results achieved? ➤ Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results?
Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it? ➤ What (if any) did not work and why?
Conclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How did the acquired results benefit the target population? ➤ Why may the intervention be considered as best practice? ➤ Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice? ➤ How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education?

Documentation should start early enough to ensure that all important ongoing activities are included, and retrospective or recalled reporting is avoided, as this may be incomplete or inaccurate. Furthermore, to ensure clarity and readability of what makes a best practice innovative, interesting and informative, *Table 1* answers should be developed extendedly (into ~1500 words' document).

4.3. *Examples of Best Practices in Gender Equality and Inclusiveness mainstreaming in Research Institutions*

Although EIGE has published [The GEAR tool step-by-step](#) on how to mainstream gender equality in EU Academia and Research, Best Practices are working as paradigms to better comprehend guidelines and instructions through documented success or failure. Five documented by [EIGE Best practices](#) in mainstreaming gender equality and inclusive education in tertiary education have been selected to assist with the implementation of the existed GEPs of both widening HEIs (UNSFAs and AUAs) participating in TALLHEDA project. Of notice the GEP of both AUA and UNSFA are following the EU guidelines, however tools and paradigms are needed to put these GEPs into action.

Table 2: Documented Best Practice Example 1

Title of the best practice	The new election procedure for the Board of Ghent University
Country	Belgium
Duration	2014 to present
Organization	University of Ghent
Contact person	<p>Dr. Tine Brouckaert Policy Officer Gender, Ghent University St. Pietersnieuwstraat 33, 9000 Gent, Belgium +32 9 264 98 38 Tine.Brouckaert@UGent.be</p>
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>What was the problem to be addressed?</i> To ensure a gender-balanced representation in the highest decision-making body of Ghent University, the university's Board of Governors (Raad van Bestuur) that since the university's foundation was male-dominated ➤ <i>Which population is affected?</i> Academic and non-academic staff, faculty members, under- and post-graduate students, PhD candidates, post-doctoral Researchers ➤ <i>How did the problem impact on the population?</i> The composition of the university's Board of Governors has been traditionally male dominated since the university was founded. Over the years, the increasing number of female professors at the university did not change the male composition and decision-making culture. That is, before the new procedure was instituted, it was a common informal practice to appoint the resigning dean of a faculty to be seated in the Board of Governors. Before the new procedure was installed, the number of female professors in this Board varied from zero to two out of 12 professor positions (or 0 to 16 %). ➤ <i>Which objectives were achieved?</i> Instead of proposing a 1/3 share of the underrepresented sex, the new institutional election procedures established a gender-balanced target ranging from 2/5 to 3/5 (or 40/60%). The

	<p>rationale behind this decision was that Ghent University wanted to anticipate the European Directive that stipulates a gender balance of minimum 60/40 for the boards of directors of companies and public institutions by 2017.</p>
<p>Implementation of the practice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the main activities carried out? In the new procedure, faculties are required to have at least one male and one female candidate for the elections. If the elections have an unbalanced gender outcome (not respecting the minimum 40/60 gender balance) the candidate with the least votes from the overrepresented sex (compared to other faculties) has to give way to the faculty's candidate of the other sex with the highest number of votes. ➤ When and where were the activities carried out? As soon as the new procedure was implemented for the first time (2014), it has instantly changed the university's male-dominated board: gender balance was achieved for the first time in the university's history. ➤ Who were the key-implementers and collaborators? All the University of Ghent faculties.
<p>Results of the practice - outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the concrete results achieved? (A) As soon as the new procedure was implemented for the first time (2014), it has instantly changed the university's male-dominated board: gender balance was achieved for the first time in the university's history. (B) The Board has now a 50/50 composition No female representative had to be positively discriminated. To the contrary, to reach the 40 per cent minimum, one woman had to give way to her male counterpart although she had more votes in total. Furthermore, the reformed election has attracted the most voters ever in the history of the University (9,268 votes) ➤ Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results? (A) Before the new procedure was installed, the number of female professors in this Board varied from zero to two out of 12 professor positions (or 0 to 16%). After the institutionalization of the new election procedure, the elections represented a significant success and meant a historic shift for gender equality at Ghent University. As a result, the Board has now a 50/50 (2025) composition. (B) Furthermore, the reformed election has attracted the most voters ever in

	the history of the University (9,268 votes), a number indicative of highly democratic procedure.
Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it?</i> The fact that Ghent University did not opt for a duo-election system in which a male and a female candidate are elected as a team because although this system initially leads to a formal compliance, informally perpetuates inequality. That is, although the duo-system often results in duos where the female candidate is the official candidate and the male candidate is the official ad interim candidate, the male candidate is seating in practice. ➤ <i>What (if any) did not work and why?</i> At the beginning there were minor opponents of the new system asking for a duo-system of election that was not voted for and at the early implementation 3 out of 11 faculties boycotted the procedure as an undemocratic one by making pre-agreements regarding who to vote for. However, persistence of the supporters of the new election system on its fundamental principles made the shift and the gender balance is now literally achieved on the board members with regard to the gender.
Conclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>How did the acquired results benefit the target population?</i> All benefits of gender equal representation in higher grade managerial positions have been achieved, including a wider range of perspectives and ideas, increased creativity and innovation and assurance that the experiences and needs of all faculty members of the organization are considered and valued. More importantly, for HEIs this can be also translated to gender equality in research opportunities and teaching activities also. ➤ <i>Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice?</i> N/A ➤ <i>How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education?</i> It strengthens the university's leadership and commitment to address gender equality in strategy, policy and delivery and directly contributes to addressing women's underrepresentation in higher education leadership. By ensuring equal male and female leaders' models 'institutional courage' in the face of gender inequality and communicating this approach

	unequivocally to partners, associates and stakeholders working in or with HEIs, discriminatory actions and omissions (i.e. restricting women’s access to higher education, restricting access to education about gender etc.) are prevented as incompatible with the core institutional values.
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Table 3: Documented Best Practice Example 2

Title of the best practice	Equal representation in applications
Country	Denmark
Duration	2014 to present
Organization	University of Copenhagen (UCPH)
Contact person	<p>Charlotte Autzen Senior Consultant University of Copenhagen KU Communications Nørregade 10, Postboks 2177 1017 København K Kommunitetsbygningen opgang C, 2. sal Bygning: 4.2.06 +45 35 32 42 64 chau@adm.ku.dk</p>
Introduction	<p>➤ <i>What was the problem to be addressed?</i> Most Danish universities suffer from the problem of retaining female researchers, especially when it comes to their further career advancements. The University of Copenhagen (UCPH) is no exception. Throughout time, and especially since 2007, UCPH has been particularly addressing the low rate of female professors by adopting a gender equality plan (2007-2013) to counteract the issue. During and after the implementation of the first GEP (2007-2013) it was found that female professors were more frequently appointed as professor MSOs (i.e. typically posts with five-year tenure) than their male colleagues. With respect to the men, during the period there was also an increase in appointments as professor MSOs but the increase was not so marked as for the women. Considering women's share of the other role categories, more women still left the</p>

	<p>University the higher up in the role category one goes. In 2014, an analysis of the university’s statistics revealed several problems in recruitment procedures. It was found that every third professor position only had one applicant, and that 36 % of the positions were filled without any female applicants (and 17 % without male).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Which population is affected? Researchers and faculty members ➤ How did the problem impact on the population? The low female application level is perceived by UCPH as a waste of good talent. Even after the first gender equality plan implementation (2008-2013), the greatest decline in the ratio of female/male faculty members occurred when transitioning from the level of assistant professor to associate professor, i.e. at the level where the normally unrestricted tenure positions are appointed. Here, women fallen from 51% of the assistant professor group to barely 35% of associate professors. Termed the “leaking pipeline”, this continued to be the reality at the University, and it was still considered nowhere near adequate. Furthermore, an analysis of the university’s statistics revealed several problems with recruitment procedures. It was found that every third professor position only had one applicant, and that 36 % of the positions were filled without any female applicants (and 17 % without male). ➤ Which objectives were achieved? Ensuring a bigger share of female academics both in entry- and higher positions. The means to achieve this goal were: 1) at least one applicant of either sex before a vacant post can be filled; 2) at least one person of each sex in all appointment and review committees; 3) Reassessment the way position vacancies are announced by introducing the use of search committees, which are to look carefully for promising candidates (inter)nationally, prior to the filling of research positions.
<p>Implementation of the practice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the main activities carried out? (1) A specific focus on the recruitment process was emphasized. After changing the internal hiring rules, there has to be at least one applicant of each sex for professor, associate professor and assistant professor positions before these positions can be filled. (2) In certain cases, the Rector can grant a dispensation when no qualified applicants of both sexes can be found. The

	<p>measure is simply a matter of ensuring that an effort is made at finding applicants of both sexes. (3) In order to remain in compliance with the law, UCPH has applied for, and been granted, a dispensation from the Equal Treatment Act. (4) Also, it has been decided to be at least one person of each sex in all UCPH appointment and review committees. (5) UCPH has also begun to reassess the way position vacancies are announced. It is considered important that both female and male applicants can see themselves in the described position and are made aware of the announcements. Accordingly, the university has reasserted the use of search committees, which are to look carefully for promising candidates (inter)nationally, prior to filling research positions. These candidates can then be given a hint about the opening. This should not only ensure a higher application rate but also make the recruitment process more open. (6) Based on the overall gender equality action plan, each faculty had to develop their own plan. These plans should be publicized on the faculty homepages, and the results of their compliance with the targets must be reported to the Rector and the Board on an annual basis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ When and where were the activities carried out? Initiated during the second gender equality plan of UCPH (2015-2017) until now ➤ Who were the key-implementers and collaborators? All UCPH faculty applicants; all UCPH appointment and review committees ➤ What were the resource implications? After having obtained a dispensation from the Danish Equal Treatment Act, the UCPH was allowed to give its faculties economic incentives to meet this goal. Hence, faculties, which hired a specific number of female professors, were awarded with an extra professorship (M/F), and the faculties that increased the ratio of newly appointed female professors by 5 % received funds from a bonus pool.
<p>Results of the practice - outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the concrete results achieved? The gender distribution among academic staff at the overall UCPH level shows that the proportion of female employees STILL declines as the career level rises. For example, the proportion of female PhD students is above 50% for all years, but this is not reflected in the proportion of female postdocs and women at higher career levels in recent

	<p>years. In other words, despite a lower proportion of male PhD students, the proportion of men who continue their career in academia at UCPH is higher than the proportion of women. This trend, whereby female employees ‘thin out’, continues as you progress up the job hierarchy. Ultimately, at professor level, the proportion of women is just over 1:4. This is the picture at most faculties, but the proportion of women at the Faculty of Law and the Faculty of Theology has fluctuated significantly during the period of 2016-2022. <u>2025 assessment results:</u> pending.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results?</i> <u>2015 assessment results:</u> 1) since 2013 there has been a positive development, so that in 2015 less faculty positions were filled where applications came from one gender; 2) the plan was being phased in, as a number of initiatives would take time to implement in its entirety, just as the effect of the overall initiatives may not be measured in just one year; 3) the need to work with the recruitment process in the form of, e.g. search committees and width in the field of applicants have already in the first year of the action plan had an effect; 4) All faculties reported that they had used search committees to all or the majority of jobs, which are advertised. ➤ <u>2016 assessment results:</u> 1) All faculties developed their own GEP. These plans are renewed and published on the faculties’ homepages, and the results of their compliance with the targets are reported to the Rector and the Board on an annual basis; 2) Increased number of newly appointed female professors by almost 10 pp; 3) Increased women’s share of Associate Professors (≥35%).
<p>Lessons learnt</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ <i>at least one person of each sex in all UCPH appointment and review committees:</i> led to increased number of newly appointed female professors while the percentage of all female representation at all academic levels was improved, though unequally. ✚ <i>the use of search committees:</i> ensure that more talents get the opportunity for a faculty position and talent became the decisive factor - not the gender. Furthermore, the proportion of female applicants is

	<p>lower, but also that the proportion of shortlisted and qualified female candidates is higher than the proportion of male applicants. This strongly indicates that the concentration of applicants who advance in the recruitment process is higher among female applicants than male applicants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What (if any) did not work and why? The proportion of women among academic staff has been improved between 2016 and 2022 by an average of 4-5 pp. This is a stable, though low rate of improvement, which, particularly in high academic positions, does not lead to impressive achievements in terms of absolute numbers or percentage changes. Furthermore, the rector, prorectors and faculty directors are still almost exclusively male, while associate deans are primarily women indicating thus an overall predominance of male academic managers at UCPH. Different choices and even the perception for the balance between work and quality of life for males and females may be the driven force of the above presented low performance, although increased domestic activities of the women are not excluded. The UCPH will re-evaluate its strategic plan after the next assessment report of 2025.
<p>Conclusion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How did the acquired results benefit the target population? The particular action plan moderate increased equal opportunities between male and female for an advanced academic career. This result certainly reinforces talent and not gender as the decisive factor for qualified academic staff employment to advance Science and Technology in Higher Education and not in favor of women in general. ➤ Why may the intervention be considered as best practice? It provides stable results although there is a slow rate of progress. ➤ Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice? The particular Action Plan for gender equality should also include actions to support women’s domestic avocation and thus create motivation for advanced academic careers because it seems that its low performance in higher academic positions is matter of choice between family (domestic occupation) and work and quality of life and work.

	<p>➤ How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education? It sets the basis for equal opportunities in academic staff recruitment. However, improvements in terms of equal gender opportunities in Research and Innovation - a more time consuming and demanding area - along with supportive to women’s domestic occupation actions should accompany the Action Plan so as both genders would be equal in qualifications and possibilities to perform also equal career evolvement in such challenging positions.</p>
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Table 4: Documented Best Practice Example 3

Title of the best practice	Gender certification
Country	Sweden
Duration	2010 to present
Organization	Lund University-Dept of Physics
Contact person	<p>Tomas Brage Professor and Director of Education in Physics Department of Physics, Lund University Box 118, 221 00 Lund, Sweden <u>+46 46 222 77 24</u> <u>tomas.brage@fysik.lu.s</u></p>
Introduction	<p>➤ What was the problem to be addressed? It has been documented by research that although academic staff are expressing willingness to work for the realization of the gender equality and inclusiveness policy, at the same time are very uncertain about how this could be done. This finding suggested that it is not enough to formulate policies, GEPs or lists of core values, and expect them to be implemented - they must be accompanied by active support and information.</p> <p>➤ Which population is affected? The academic staff to perform excellence in activities related to their HEI’s GEP</p>

	<p>and consequently women performing or willing to perform an academic career of high expectations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How did the problem impact on the population? Although the design of a DEC is mandatory for all European HEIs - especially those related to EU funding - the implementation lacks behind especially in widening countries due to lack of information and robust support. ➤ Which objectives were achieved? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. “Education, Information and “Infiltration” activities to introduce gender equality and inclusiveness perception that promoted creative dialogue between all involved including faculty members, administrative staff and students B. “Realizing ideas” where innovative and inclusive educational ideas and activities from the phase of “Education, Information and “Infiltration” were carried out to inform faculty members, administrative staff and students about gender equality and inclusiveness benefits in HEIs including creation of ideas, and breakthrough research and innovation. C. Evaluation of the outcome.
<p>Implementation of the practice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What were the main activities carried out? 1) <u>Initiation of the pilot project to assist in the implementation of gender equality policies of the university</u> <p>The one-year pilot project investigated the concept of gender certification and provided suggestions, in the form of questions, of criteria for certification. The concept of certification was interpreted as some form of quality assurance. It stressed that self-assessment is important to create activity and dialogue, but it also needs to be extended to involve a third-party evaluation.</p> <p>The report of the pilot project listed suggestions on how to implement self-assessment by answering questions in four areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Gender awareness</i>, which concerns the culture in the institutions. Examples of questions for this criterion are: Is everybody given the same opportunity to be seen and heard? Are exams anonymous? Are different forms of examination used?

2. *Gender Perspective*, which concerns the subject matter. The following questions were used for this particular criterion: Are teachers given the opportunity to learn about gender research linked to their subject of research and teaching? Are concepts in and the content of a course or research problematized from a gender perspective?
3. *Plans and strategies*, which raise questions on how gender equality is introduced, followed up and implemented.
4. *Protection against discrimination* contains questions about how the department works to prevent harassment and discrimination.

- 2) Invitation from the Vice Chancellor to all Departments to participate in the certification project. Department of Physics, Earth Sciences and Energy Sciences responded
- 3) Gender Certification project implementation by the Dept. of Physics

For Part (A) “Education, Information and “Infiltration” main activities included:

- ✚ A **workshop** about discrimination ‘See the Human Beyond’. The Swedish Discrimination Act was discussed from a norm-critical perspective. This workshop also included a presentation of research in the field, and used bias tests, case studies and assessments to create discussion on the culture of the institute.
- ✚ A **symposium** with experts on Gender and Science: ‘What does Gender have to do with Physics?’.
- ✚ A reference group with people representing different divisions and categories of personnel. Information meetings about the project were held and questionnaires were distributed.
- ✚ A **course** on ‘Gender in Science and Technology’ both for students and teachers (this course is still being organized nowadays).
- ✚ A **symposium** on ‘Gender Perspectives and Gender Awareness - how can we implement change of culture and subject at the Physics department?’. The first half-day introduced the topics and the second brought up possible activities to be implemented in the second step

For part (B) “Realizing ideas” main activities included:

- ✚ A **brochure** with a credit-card-size for wallet with information about Gender and Physics which was distributed to students. It also contained information on where to turn, if a student had experienced discrimination or harassment.
- ✚ A **new type of questions** was included in course evaluations regarding gender and equality issues.
- ✚ A **symposium** on ‘Gendered Innovations’ by Londa Schiebinger.
- ✚ A **bookshelf** with Gender and Science literature in the Physics library. This bookshelf was also sent around the lunchrooms of the Department.
- ✚ A **Gender Coach was employed** for a year, acting as a resource for the Department in its gender work. The coach was invited to analyze the Department’s budget from a gender perspective.
- ✚ A **parental leave reform for PhD and Post-docs was conducted**. It was decided to give a double extension of the appointment when parental leave was used (e.g. if a PhD is on parental leave for four months, one can apply for an extension of up to eight months).

For Part (C) **Evaluation** main activities included

- ✚ A “**Book of Methods**”
- ✚ A short **evaluation** of the outcome.

➤ ***When and where were the activities carried out?***

2007 - March 2008: A *gender certification pilot project* was applied by the Vice Chancellor of Lund University.

December 2008 to date: Department of Physics *Certification Project*

Who were the key implementers and collaborators?

For the pilot project: representatives from all faculties, along with representatives from the union, students and administrative personnel.

For the certification project: all Dept. of Physics faculty members, along with representatives from the union, students and administrative personnel

For the mainstreaming: In 2010, a working team has been appointed to share information about the project within the departments of Physics, Earth Sciences and Energy Sciences

	<p>and to discuss, initiate and implement various activities. The gender certification group (the working team) was meeting on a regular basis to plan the projects' activities and to bring them further.</p> <p>➤ <i>What were the resource implications?</i> N/A</p>
<p>Results of the practice - outputs</p>	<p>➤ <i>What were the concrete results achieved?</i> 1)The project has changed the gender perception philosophy of the participating departments. It became clear from the project's experience that the existence of a goal - a certification - focused the work; 2) The fact that criteria gave suggestions on what to work on was an important support for the organization and helped to reach a larger group of people; 3) A brief analysis, using techniques from the 'Gender Certification' project, shows that all involved worked on understanding gender assumptions in their teaching and research through workshops. This led to rethinking teaching, changing concepts and languages, and possibly also changed research questions and priorities. This change is currently being investigated by collecting statistics and by conducting interviews. The purpose is to better understand the process and to be able to give advice for the future; 4) Another change concerns the gender group. It started with only male researchers and students and few years later (2010), they managed to attract a significant number of women from all involved groups (faculty members, administrative staff and students).</p> <p>➤ <i>Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results?</i> <u>2010</u>: concrete results above</p>
<p>Lessons learnt</p>	<p>➤ <i>What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The pilot project: it defined the criteria for the certification and set a common basis of comprehending gender equality and inclusiveness in HEIs. ○ The active participation of all involved stakeholders representing different groups of HEIs' employees. ○ The implementation of activities that have been co-created and co-implemented by all involved stakeholders ○ The Book of Methods that is ready to use by any department, faculty or university willing to educate

	<p>personnel and students on how to comprehend gender equality and inclusiveness in HEIs so as to facilitate the implementation of GEPs</p> <p>➤ <i>What (if any) did not work and why?</i> N/A</p>
Conclusion	<p>➤ <i>How did the acquired results benefit the target population?</i> They are aware of how to prepare and implement a feasible GEP tailored to their needs.</p> <p>➤ <i>Why may the intervention be considered as best practice?</i> It concluded in a tailored to the needs of their HEI department Book of Methods for how to implement education and training in gender equality and inclusive education</p> <p>➤ <i>Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice?</i> N/A</p> <p>➤ <i>How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education?</i> The GEP produced by people certified in awareness of gender equality and inclusive education is adjusted to their needs and cover aspects their particular HEI faces and thus have increased possibilities of successful implementation. In addition, it sets the basis to develop gender expertise and thus prioritizes gender mainstreaming.</p>

Table 5: Documented Best Practice EXAMPLE 4

Title of the best practice	Workshop: Bias-sensitizing - Quality assurance for personnel selection
Country	Austria
Duration	2010 to present
Organization	University of Graz
Contact person	<p>Dr. Barbara Hey, MBA</p> <p>Head of Unit Coordination Centre for Gender Studies/Research and Equal Opportunities, University Graz.</p> <p>Beethovenstraße 19, 8010 Graz, Austria</p> <p><u>+43 316 380 - 5722</u></p>

	barbara.hey@uni-graz.at
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>What was the problem to be addressed?</i> The bias sensitizing workshop aims to address a particular problem: <u>contribute to the understanding that the goal of equality coincides with the goal of quality and excellence.</u> ➤ <i>Which population is affected?</i> All university employees (faculty members and administrative staff) and especially members of faculty and administrative election committees ➤ <i>How did the problem impact on the population?</i> An extensive body of academic research shows that selection procedures for academic personnel are shaped by gender bias. Gender bias in personnel selection is based on effects of homophile and male networks, as well as on gender stereotypes and masculine imagery of the ideal academic. Considering that the identity, and the main task, of universities and academics is to conduct high-quality teaching and research, gender equality, when understood as contradictory to this aim, can be perceived as illegitimate. If the main criterion for decision-making in personnel selection procedures is to identify the candidate who is of the highest quality and best fit for the job, then criteria that take into account other issues, such as for example gender equality, are often seen as misplaced in these procedures. ➤ <i>Which objectives were achieved?</i> To increase awareness for this subtle and invisible mechanism, which perpetuates gender inequality in academia, the University of Graz is conducting, since 2010, a bias-sensitizing training module as part of their general leadership training programme. The main objective is to improve the overall quality of personnel selection procedures.
Implementation of the practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>What were the main activities carried out?</i> The training module consists of two main sets of activities: A. Activities to widen the attendance of the workshop on Bias-sensitizing. These activities include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Integration of the workshop as an optional module in the university’s overall training programme for leadership personnel. This lifted the training from an

isolated gender-specific activity to an integral part of leadership development.

- ✚ Attendance in the training can be brought forward as a justification for not fulfilling the legally prescribed gender quota for decision-making bodies.
- ✚ The training is framed explicitly as a measure towards increasing the quality of decision-making for recruitment procedures and not as an equality activity

B. Workshop activities on Bias-sensitizing.

The training workshop takes place over two half-day sessions of five hours each, with about one month in between these sessions.

The **first session** focuses on diversity, as well as on the effects of expectations and societal inequalities on evaluations and decisions. It is facilitated by a trainer from the Austrian Society for Diversity, i.e. external to the university. This first session consists of an input about diversity issues and bias effects, and it promotes reflection and discussion.

The **second session** focuses on the formation of scientific reputation and the practice of evaluating academic curricula vitae. It is facilitated by members of the university's equal treatment commission, the university's coordination centers for gender studies/research and equal opportunities, as well as an external expert specialized in academic consulting. This session mostly consists of a group exercise. In this exercise, participants take the role of evaluators in a mock selection procedure. The candidate profiles are designed so as to contain CV elements which reflect the most common evaluation biases of different underrepresented groups, including a number of gender specific career trajectories such as, for example, childcare time.

- **When and where were the activities carried out?**
University of Graz, Austria from 2010 to present
- **Who were the key-implementers and collaborators?**
This training is targeted at members of academic personnel at the university, who fulfil internal administration duties as members of committees in decision-making bodies. The educators are members of the university's equal treatment commission, the

	<p>university's coordination centers for gender studies/research and equal opportunities, as well as an external expert specialized in academic consulting (i.e. from the Austrian Society for Diversity)</p>
<p>Results of the practice - outputs</p>	<p>➤ <i>What were the concrete results achieved?</i> Towards improving the overall quality of personnel selection procedures, if the main criterion for decision-making in personnel selection procedures is to identify the candidate who is of the highest quality and best fit for the job, then criteria that take into account other issues, such as for example gender equality, are often seen as misplaced in these procedures.</p> <p>The results of the workshop include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Identification and circulation of the problem:</i> what is believed to be a bias-free, objective decision in personnel selection is rather strongly shaped by societal beliefs and inequalities. ○ <i>Improving the quality of decision-making</i> in recruitment and hiring procedures via increasing the knowledge and awareness of electors' bias in decision-making. ○ <i>Contributing to a wider academic community transformation</i> in the understanding of equality and diversity work <p>➤ <i>Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results?</i> N/A</p>
<p>Lessons learnt</p>	<p>➤ <i>What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it?</i> 1) The second (practical) session, focusing on the formation of scientific reputation and the practice of evaluating academic curricula vitae. This session consists of group exercise; participants take the role of evaluators in a mock selection procedure. The candidate profiles are designed so as to contain CV elements which reflect the most common evaluation biases of different underrepresented groups, including several gender specific career trajectories such as, for example, childcare time. These activities provide actual, hands-on experience for the present and future members of election committees. 2) Because of the high quality of the training, and particularly because of the revelatory character of the group exercise (mock evaluation procedure and reflective discussion), the word-of-mouth</p>

	<p>of participants created a high reputation and attractiveness of the workshop. Since 2013, the possibility to participate in this training has been extended to other universities (through the payment of a fee). For instance, the personnel of the Danube University of Krems have been participating in this training on a regular basis.</p> <p>➤ <i>What (if any) did not work and why?</i> N/A</p>
<p>Conclusion</p>	<p>➤ <i>How did the acquired results benefit the target population?</i> Taking into consideration societal and other bias including gender, inclusiveness and other discrimination issues, in personnel selection makes the process fair and equal for all candidates. Consequently, a fair and equal process increases the quality of education and research excellence in HEIs. Furthermore, participants gain knowledge about diversity issues, societal inequalities, and academic evaluation procedures. They also participate in a simulated personnel selection procedure, as well as discussions on academic curricula vitae, to trigger reflection about their own selection criteria, prejudice and biases.</p> <p>➤ <i>Why may the intervention be considered as best practice?</i> Because of the quality of training and especially the revelatory character of the group exercise (mock evaluation procedure and reflective discussion) that proved to increase knowledge and awareness by hands-on experience in simulated personnel selection procedures and attractiveness of the training module leading thus to its successful upscaling.</p> <p>➤ <i>Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice?</i> N/A</p> <p>➤ <i>How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education?</i> Ensuring a fair and equal, by all means, personnel selection process -and not standing on explicitly scientific excellence criteria- gender equality is instantly promoted. In addition, gender equality issues are co-treated with other discrimination issues like racial, religion and socio-economic issues, promoting a wave of change in adopting the inclusive culture. Furthermore, it contributes to developing gender expertise and in asserting centrality of equality and inclusivity to the definition of quality and excellence in higher education and research.</p>

Table 6: Documented Best Practice Example 5

Title of the best practice	Gender & Diversity Controlling at Goethe University Frankfurt
Country	Germany
Duration	2010 to present
Organization	Goethe University
Contact person	<p>Annemarie Mlakar Coordinator, Gender & Diversity Controlling Goethe University Frankfurt Theodor-W.-Adorno-Platz 1, 60323 Frankfurt am Main, Germany +496979818123 mlakar@em.uni-frankfurt.de</p>
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What was the problem to be addressed? It had been realized that the level of commitment to design and implementing gender equality measures differed significantly between the decentral units of Goethe University while a need for centralizing information on gender equality initiatives in the faculties was deemed necessary. ➤ Which population is affected? All university employees (faculty members and administrative staff) and students and especially university managers who could not evaluate the status of implementation and the progress of Faculties’ GEPs so as to provide corrective improvement actions. ➤ How did the problem impact on the population? Faculties’ GEPs implementation were not monitored effectively to accurately measure the status and the progress in gender equality and inclusiveness in the particular HEI’s departments and faculties. ➤ Which objectives were achieved? The Gender & Diversity Controlling Unit provides services including 1) monitoring development with respect to gender (in)equalities across the university; 2) guidance and support, and monitoring gender equality-related

	<p><i>efforts</i> within the 16 faculties of Goethe University Frankfurt. In addition, the <i>coordinator</i> of the unit oversees the steering of the controlling/monitoring procedures and manages the compilation of gender & diversity statistics within the university. That is, the unit systematically carries out Gender Equality Monitoring of the share of female and male staff in different positions and in different decision-making bodies, amongst others.</p>
<p>Implementation of the practice</p>	<p>➤ <i>What were the main activities carried out?</i> The Gender & Diversity Controlling unit guides the faculties' representatives via a specific actions' circular pathway: (1) analysis of the status quo and needs assessment; (2) planning of gender equality measures addressing the identified needs; (3) implementation of these measures; and (4) assessment of successes and shortcomings of the measures, as well as issuing recommendations. This multi-step and multidisciplinary process involves:</p> <p>A first step in the process, where the Gender & Diversity Controlling coordinator provides the faculties with sex-disaggregated statistics, tools to assist them in the reporting and planning process, and further relevant material if deemed necessary.</p> <p>A second step where the faculties have to analyze the status quo, to assess existing measures and to design their next GEP within three months. At least one Gender & Diversity Consulting meeting takes place with each faculty, complemented by less formalized forms of exchange. During this meeting, the Gender & Diversity Controlling coordinators, as well as experts from 'Gender Consulting' and the 'Family Service', provide an initial feedback and advice with regard to identified needs and promising initiatives. This meeting is also aimed at finding a shared understanding about the priority areas of intervention (as usually resources are limited). These experts are brought together in order to make use of the available in-house expertise in different fields of action. They support the faculties in setting up tailor-made measures addressing the identified individual needs. It is up to the faculties to decide who will take part in these meetings from their side. Typically, the following representatives take part of these meetings: the Dean or his/her deputies, the Head of the faculty's administration or Head or member of the faculty's quality management unit, the coordinator of study/teaching issues within the</p>

faculty (who is most likely a member of the research/teaching staff, and the faculty's women's representative (who may be a researcher and/or a member of the administrative staff)).

The **third step** involves the designing of Faculties next GEPs following guidelines and templates. Once they submit the action plans to the Gender & Diversity Controlling coordinator, the unit assesses the plans and issues a comprehensive report. Subsequently, the University Senate's Commission on Gender Equality and Diversity receives the action plans together with the assessment made by the Gender & Diversity Controlling unit and provides written feedback to the respective faculties.

The **fourth step** is about the assessment of the GEPs, the quality criteria defined in the Research-Oriented Standards on Gender Equality of the German Research Foundation (DFG) are applied, namely consistency, transparency, competitiveness and forward-looking approach, and competency. These criteria are complemented by the following two criteria: the extent to which the measures fit the context and the objectives (i.e. if they respond adequately to the problems identified); and how the measures address the needs of their target groups orientation. The faculties have the power to decide on the modification of their action plans based on the feedback received.

- ***When and where were the activities carried out?*** From 2010 until today the Goethe University Frankfurt applies Genders and Diversity Controlling via an integrated process (identified as good practice by EIGE) that demands report and evaluation of all Faculties' GEP activities to revise it as needed every two years.
- ***Who were the key-implementers and collaborators?*** Gender and Diversity Controlling is applied by the corresponding university unit (Gender & Diversity Controlling Unit). The coordinator of the Gender & Diversity Controlling Unit is a member of the Equal Opportunities Office, who cooperates closely with the university's central reporting and controlling unit. The coordinator is supported by a team to undertake the controlling/monitoring tasks, composed of coordinators of other fields of activity of the Equality Opportunities Office, namely 'Gender Consulting', 'Diversity Consulting'

	<p>and ‘Family Service’. The Unit’s provided services are sought by management staff, administrators and researchers. This unit carries out Gender Equality Monitoring of the share of female and male staff in different positions and in different decision-making bodies, amongst others.</p>
<p>Results of the practice - outputs</p>	<p>➤ <i>What were the concrete results achieved?</i> 1) The Gender Equality and Diversity Action Plans at faculty level have been significantly developed and advanced in comparison to previous reporting periods.</p> <p>Gender Equality & Diversity measures tend to have a larger scope than before and are more likely to be successfully implemented. 2)</p> <p>The active involvement of a variety of stakeholders in gender equality-related efforts within the faculties has increased over the years. 3) A complete statistical record related to gender quality issues has been developed.</p> <p>➤ <i>Was an assessment of the practice carried out? If yes, what were the results?</i></p> <p>2012 assessment results: After the first two controlling/monitoring rounds, the Gender & Diversity Controlling prepared a report to analyze the results and effects achieved so far, including an assessment of strong and weak points of the procedures. This ‘Self-Evaluation’ was then reviewed by the university Senate’s Commission on Gender Equality and Diversity. Based on this review, some amendments were made to the procedure, which was implemented in the next round.</p> <p>2014 assessment results: The Gender & Diversity Controlling approach and procedures have proven very promising at Goethe University Frankfurt. They have met the needs for central steering and monitoring, while granting the faculties freedom to design and implement tailor-made action plans. Gender & Diversity Controlling makes gender equality-related efforts within the faculties more binding and supports informed action with regard to gender equality. The different elements and services provided by the Gender & Diversity Controlling unit are considered to contribute to the acceptance and success of the controlling/monitoring procedures.</p> <p>2016 assessment results: This structure is embedded in a wider strategy and in the organization, which ensures</p>

	<p>its continuity and sustainability. It adopts a participatory and inclusive approach by ensuring the involvement of the University’s Senate, faculties’ representatives, along with other structures of the university (such as experts from Gender Consulting and the ‘Family Service’). The controlling/monitoring procedures and tools are effective for learning how to act upon existing inequalities.</p>
<p>Lessons learnt</p>	<p><i>What worked really well and which parameters facilitated it?</i> 1) The circular nature of the process makes the effort meaningful since every round is concluded in measurable results of the process’ s outcomes leading to that led to updates of the Faculties’ GEPs every two years. In the same context, the coordinator prepares and shares sex-disaggregated statistics including, amongst others, comparisons over time and an assessment of the achievement of the action plans’ objectives; 2) From 2010 to date, several tools have been developed in order to guide and assist actors at faculty level throughout the process. These tools are continuously being updated and adjusted and have become well-accepted among their target group. Particularly, at the beginning of each phase of reporting activities, the Gender & Diversity Controlling coordinator provides the faculties with the following tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines on how to carry out a baseline and a needs assessment, how to define priority objectives and how to identify target groups, together with a reporting template • A template for documenting the assessment of measures implemented regarding a reporting period • A template for developing new measures to be implemented in the upcoming reporting period, including the definition of objectives, target groups, costs and responsibilities • A toolkit featuring exemplary measures at faculty level. <p>➤ <i>What (if any) did not work and why?</i> Having overcome some initial resistances, this process is well-established and accepted by now. However, subtle resistance remains among a few stakeholders that is shown in a low level of cooperation with the coordinator and the disregard of advice. The resistance is likely to be rooted in the concern of some researchers that such controlling instruments restrict their freedom in decision-making and research</p>

	<p>and impose labor-intensive administrative duties. Yet, most stakeholders tend to accept and appreciate the controlling/monitoring process once they are more familiar with it and its aims. For example, the broad acceptance of the initiative is more likely if the objectives of the controlling/monitoring that are to be communicated are aligned with the university's and faculties' objectives, e.g. those related to scientific and research excellence.</p>
<p>Conclusion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>How did the acquired results benefit the target population?</i> 1) The results came from a uniformed and unbiased model for monitoring and controlling gender equality and inclusivity in universities and led to actually applied gender equality for all involved; 2) Training and education as well as tools provided increased awareness and know-how to act upon existing inequalities incidences and led to their elimination; 3) They strengthen organizational leadership and commitment to address gender equality in strategy, policy, quality assurance and delivery ➤ <i>Why may the intervention be considered as best practice?</i> 1) It is a long lifecycle, intersectional, inclusive and successful approach that provides unbiased records statistical results on gender equality and inclusive education in HEIs; 2) In this framework the process has met the needs for central steering and monitoring, while granting the faculties freedom to design and implement tailor-made action plans; 3) Gender & Diversity Controlling makes gender equality-related efforts within the faculties more binding and supports informed action with regard to gender equality; 4) The particular structure is embedded in a wider strategy and in the organization, which ensures its continuity and sustainability; 5) The controlling/monitoring procedures and tools are good for learning how to act upon existing inequalities; 6) The Gender & Diversity Controlling model designed and implemented at Goethe University Frankfurt is likely to be transferable to other Universities with adaptations. ➤ <i>Are there any considerations or tips for HEIs intending to adopt the documented best practice?</i> The Gender & Diversity Controlling model designed and implemented at Goethe University Frankfurt presents a long-life success and thus is likely to be transferable to other Universities.

	<p>Certain adaptations may have to be considered depending on each specific HEI context of organization so the circular 4-steps process will not lose its intersectional and holistic nature.</p> <p>➤ <i>How can the documented best practice help tackling gender inequalities and promote inclusiveness in higher education?</i> 1) The applied circular, intersectional and lifecycle approach ensures long impact on HEIs gender equality and inclusiveness by incorporating long-term planning, monitoring and evaluation processes; 2) It strengthen organizational leadership and commitment to address gender equality in strategy, policy, quality assurance and delivery and thus concluding in actual gender equality and inclusiveness In addition every gender equality controversial act, if any, is immediately perceived and recorded as an example of avoidance.</p>
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Best practices that are not yet documented by EIGE, although promising for mainstreaming gender equality and inclusive education and specifically addressing GBV in HEIs are listed below.

- [active consent programme](#), National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland,
- [code of ethics and deontology](#), Transilvania University in Brasov, Romania,
- [guidelines for equal treatment](#), University of Tartu, Estonia,
- ['It starts with ME, together WE can' - annual innovative campaign and public intervention in cases of violence against women](#), Frederick University, Cyprus,
- [protocol against gender-based violence](#), University of the Basque Country, Spain,
- [protocol on gender-based and sexual violence](#), Network of the Gender Equality Committees of Greek Universities, Greece,
- [zero tolerance](#), Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium

